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CLINICAL AND LABORATORY FEATURES OF CONGENITAL PNEUMONIA IN NEWBORN BABIES

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ABSTRACT

Respiratory diseases continue to lead among the causes of child and infant mortality. The role of the pathology of the bronchopulmonary system among the causes of morbidity and mortality in newborns is especially great. This article provides information on the clinical and laboratory aspects of congenital pneumonia in newborns and analyzes the work of scientists who have conducted research in recent years.

Keywords: disease monitoring, clinical and laboratory, bronchopulmonary system, intranatal, intensive care.

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КЛИНИКО-ЛАБОРАТОРНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ВРОЖДЕННОЙ ПНЕВМОНИИ У НОВОРОЖДЕННЫХ ДЕТЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Заболевания органов дыхания продолжают лидировать среди причин детской и младенческой смертности. Особенно велика роль патологии бронхолегочной системы среди причин заболеваемости и смертности новорожденных. В данной статье представлены сведения о клинико-лабораторных аспектах врожденной пневмонии у новорожденных и проанализированы работы ученых, проводивших исследования последних лет.

Ключевые слова: мониторинг заболевания, клинико-лабораторный, бронхолегочная система, интранатально, интенсивная терапия.

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YANGI TUG‘ILGAN CHAQALOQLARDA TUG‘MA PNEVMONIYANING KLINIK- LABORATORIYA JIHATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Nafas olish tizimi kasalliklari bolalar va go‘daklar o‘limi sabablari orasida yetakchilik qilishda davom etmoqda. Yangi tug‘ilgan chaqaloqlarda kasallanish va o‘lim sabablari orasida bronxopulmoner tizim patologiyasining roli kattadir. Ushbu maqola yangi tug‘ilgan chaqaloqlarda tug‘ma pnevmoniyaning klinik- laboratoriya jihatlari haqida ma'lumot beradi va so'nggi yillarda tadqiqot olib borgan olimlarning ishlari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: kasalliklar monitoringi, klinik - laboratoriya, bronxopulmoner tizim, intranatal, intensiv terapiya.

Relevance. Congenital pneumonias are one of the leading causes in the structure of infant mortality and account for 16% [6]. Congenital pneumonia is an acute infectious and inflammatory disease of the respiratory parts of the lungs as a result of ante- and / or intranatal infection, which has clinical and radiological manifestations in the first 72 hours of a child's life (ICD code X - P23) [11].

According to official statistics, the incidence of pneumonia is about 1% among full-term and about 10% among premature babies and reaches 40% in newborns in the intensive care unit, with various types of respiratory therapy [3,5].

A huge role in the development of pneumonia is given to modifiable risk factors: aggravated obstetric and gynecological history of the mother, severe disorders of the central nervous system, malnutrition II-III degree; congenital malformations, etc. Predisposing factors that affect the immunological reactivity of the body play a role in the development of congenital pneumonia in newborns [6,15].

WHO notes the relevance of research on the identification of causative agents of pneumonia in children, as this is of decisive importance for etiotropic treatment. However, the identification of pathogens presents certain difficulties. The etiological structure of congenital pneumonia in newborns differs significantly from other age periods [12,19].

Newborn mortality was 40% of the total number of dead children [22]. In 2015, 2.7 million children died in the neonatal period. The leading causes of neonatal death are prematurity and pneumonia. Preterm birth and pneumonia are significant in countries with high, medium, and low infant mortality rates [23,24]. The efforts of the world community for many decades have been aimed at reducing neonatal and infant mortality, including those from intrauterine infections [2].

Currently, there is an increase in the incidence of congenital pneumonia in full-term newborns. This is a serious disease of the newborn, which has a significant impact on the further physical development of the child, can contribute to the formation of chronic bronchopulmonary disease, allergic processes, and a decrease in immunological reactivity, so the study of the clinical features of congenital pneumonia remains an urgent problem in modern pediatrics.

There is no comparative characteristic of the diagnostic significance of the levels of PCT, CRP in the blood serum of children with congenital pneumonia. Therefore, there is a need to develop other, innovative approaches that can provide early, fast and accurate diagnosis, effective therapy and monitoring of the clinical condition of such children in dynamics. From this point of view, the use of modern biochemical and microbiological methods seems promising, as well as in monitoring the effectiveness of the treatment of newborn children. The preservation of their health largely depends on the timely and high-quality provision of medical services to premature babies.

This circumstance makes it expedient and relevant to conduct this study, emphasizes the scientific and practical significance of the formulated goals and objectives.

Purpose of the study. To analyze the work of scientists who have studied the clinical and laboratory aspects of congenital pneumonia in newborns in recent years and prepare a review of the literature.

Material and research methods. The methodology of this study is planned based on modern principles of scientific knowledge [25]. The subject of the study was the problems associated with the clinical and laboratory aspects of congenital pneumonia in newborns. The analysis of scientific literature devoted to the problem of clinical and laboratory aspects of congenital pneumonia in newborns was carried out on the basis of formal logical research methods.

Research results of scientists. Perinatal pathology ranks first in the structure of infant morbidity and mortality. Preterm birth still remains an important medical and social problem, because. cause high morbidity and mortality in premature newborns. In the early neonatal period, severely preterm infants with low body weight (ELBW) are most often diagnosed with the incidence of sepsis and congenital infections, this figure reaches 26%, which, in turn, causes high neonatal mortality [13,25].

Regardless of the level of infant mortality, the most common causes of neonatal death are prematurity and congenital pneumonia [2,4]. The incidence is higher in preterm infants (10% - 15%) than in term infants (1%). And in newborns who are in intensive care units on mechanical ventilation, the incidence of pneumonia can reach 40% [6,25].

The introduction of new treatment technologies into practice has improved the success of nursing such newborns, including those with morphofunctional immaturity. However, the incidence of adverse outcomes remains very high [7].

In the pathogenesis of lung lesions in newborns, especially premature infants, the immaturity of bronchopulmonary structures, surfactant deficiency, and metabolic disorders are essential [17].

The frequency of congenital pneumonia with an extremely severe and "fulminant" course has increased, antibiotic-resistant strains of bacteria appear, which complicate the therapy and monitoring of the disease. Most often, pneumonia in newborns is caused by *Staphylococcus aureus*, including methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Proteus spp.*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter spp.*, *Enterobacter spp.* [20].

In recent years, many researchers have emphasized the high diagnostic significance of determining the level of C-reactive protein (CRP) and procalcitonin (PCT) in blood serum as one of the newest biomarkers of the systemic inflammatory response. An elevated PCT level for a long time indicates an unfavorable course of the disease and is most often explained by ineffective therapy [8].

It has been established that newborns, both premature and full-term, belong to one of the most susceptible groups for the development of vitamin D deficiency. It has been shown that vitamin D deficiency is observed in more than half of mothers and newborns [12,18]. The supply of vitamin D to the fetus and newborn directly depends on the content of vitamin D in the mother. According to the literature, vitamin D significantly affects the development of the lungs of a child during its prenatal development, including the synthesis of surfactant. It is also assumed that hypovitaminosis D has a negative effect on the formation of the central nervous system [1,6,26].

Pathology of the respiratory system is one of the main causes of high morbidity and mortality in newborns. Infections characteristic of the perinatal period account for about 30% in the structure of causes of infant mortality. Among respiratory diseases in the neonatal period, pneumonia occupies a special place due to the high frequency, severity of the course, the possibility of complications and adverse outcomes. Pneumonia is the most important single infectious cause of death in children worldwide [4,7,10].

According to official statistics, in 2015, congenital pneumonia was diagnosed in 0.98% of premature newborns with a birth weight of 1000 g or more and in 20.77% of newborns from 500 to 999 g. Mortality from congenital pneumonia in full-term newborns was 1, 66%, premature babies born with a body weight of 1000 g or more - 2.3%, children born with extremely low body weight - 11.8%.

Pneumonia is a form of acute respiratory infection that affects the lungs. This is an acute infectious disease of predominantly bacterial etiology, characterized by damage to the respiratory sections of the lungs with intraalveolar exudation, infiltration by inflammatory cells and impregnation of the parenchyma with exudate, the presence of previously absent clinical and radiological signs of local inflammation that are not associated with other causes [16,23].

The onset of spontaneous breathing is one of the most important factors in the child's adaptation to ectopic existence, intrauterine and intranatal infections, and the development of the inflammatory process is one of the main reasons for the high incidence of respiratory adaptation disorders [14].

Worldwide, about 1.7 million child deaths are associated with pneumonia, and a significant number of them occur in low-income countries [27]. Approximately 0.5-1.0% of newborns and 10-15% of premature newborns are diagnosed with pneumonia. And in newborns who are in the NICU on mechanical ventilation, the incidence of pneumonia can reach 40% [25].

In the Russian Federation, according to the Ministry of Health, the incidence of pneumonia in newborns has not changed much over the past 5 years and does not have a downward trend of up to 85% (form No. 32 of Rosstat Decree No. 2520 dated December 29, 2011) [28].

According to some researchers, chest radiography in most cases has a low diagnostic level, although it is a well-known method for diagnosing pneumonia. In their opinion, fever and tachypnea are important diagnostic signs of pneumonia in newborns [29].

At the same time, it must be taken into account that during the neonatal period, pneumonia manifests itself as a picture of respiratory diseases, and clinical manifestations of focal and systemic inflammation can be expressed to a slight extent.

For this reason, the diagnosis of pneumonia in the neonatal period can be considered verified only in cases where focal inflammatory lung injury is confirmed radiologically [15].

According to N.N. Volodin, the main criteria for diagnosing intrauterine pneumonia are:

- focal and / or infiltrative shadows are noted on the x-ray (in the first 3 days of life);
- when sowing clinical material from a puerperal woman and a newborn of a similar microbiota (material should be taken on the first day of life);
- the development of pneumonia with aspiration syndrome, during the first 3 days of life (if aspiration occurred intranatally and was confirmed by suction from the trachea immediately after the birth of the child).

The presence of one of these criteria is evidence of the development of intrauterine pneumonia [22].

There are some differences in the terminology of "congenital pneumonia". A number of researchers adhere to the definition that pneumonia associated with antenatal infection should be understood as diseases that are clinically manifested in the first three days of a child's life. With intranatal infection, VUP can also develop during the first 72 hours of life [28]. However, it is known that intrauterine pneumonia can manifest itself later - on the 4th-7th day of life and with some types of pathogens, for example, in *C. trachomatis*, at 3-6-8 weeks of life [28, 30].

According to Y. J. Wang, et al. (2010) it is inappropriate to classify pneumonias as either congenital or acquired based solely on the timing of onset of clinical symptoms before and more than 72 hours after birth. It is more reasonable to subdivide pneumonia into early (most often congenital) and late (most often acquired) [30].

Along with this, WHO experts point out the difficulties in the differential diagnosis between congenital and nosocomial pneumonia in the detection of pneumonia in newborns over the age of 2 days who are in a maternity hospital.

Bogomazov A. D. [9] proposes to divide neonatal pneumonia into:

- congenital transplacental (antenatal);
- congenital intranatal pneumonia;
- neonatal acquired pneumonia (including home and hospital pneumonia). Of the latter, it is recommended to isolate ventilator-associated pneumonia against the background of mechanical ventilation.

According to the clinical guidelines "Congenital pneumonia" of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation (2017), it is recommended to use the more capacious term "neonatal pneumonia", combining congenital, aspiration and acquired, including nosocomial pneumonia of newborns [11].

The development of pneumonia in newborns is favored by a large number of adverse factors affecting the fetus in the prenatal, intra- and postnatal periods.

Neonatal pneumonia can be both a primordial disease and one of the foci of septicemia or a viral infection.

The etiology of neonatal pneumonia is polymorphic and depends on the time and circumstances of entry of the infectious agent into the lungs. In the vast majority of cases, intrauterine pneumonia that occurs in the antenatal period is one of the manifestations of a specific IUI (cytomegaly virus, herpes infection, listeriosis, etc.). The presence of pure viral pneumonia is not recognized by all authors. It is believed that viruses are conductors that prepare the ground for the attachment of intracellular pathogens [25].

According to most researchers, intrauterine transplacental (antenatal) pneumonia is a manifestation of generalized IUI, such as rubella, herpes, listeriosis, mycoplasmosis, etc. Antenatal infection is possible with group B and D streptococci, listeria monocytogens, etc.

It is emphasized that congenital intranatal infections are the result of genital infectious diseases of the mother with the corresponding microflora:

- genital mycoplasmas (*M. hominis*, *U. urealyticum*);
- anaerobic bacteria, including group B and D streptococci;
- other microorganisms - green streptococci, hemophilic and tubercle bacilli, listeria.

Intranatal pneumonia acquired during childbirth is caused by group B streptococcus, chlamydia, *M. hominis*, CMV, listeria, HSV-2, fungi of the genus *Candida*, less often other pathogens - viridescens streptococcus, *Escherichia coli*, enterococci, trichomonads [14].

Acquired (hospital, nosocomial) pneumonia can be caused by *K. pneumoniae*, *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*, and home "street" acquired pneumonia is more common against the background of acute respiratory viral infection (ARVI) caused by adenoviruses, respiratory syncytial virus etc. with attachment of pneumococci or hemophilic rod [25]. A similar species composition is characteristic of early ventilators of associated pneumonia. Late pneumonias are caused by *P. aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter*, *Serratia*, *S. epidermidis* and *S. aureus*, including methicillin-resistant ones, often in combination with fungi of the genus *Candida*, mycoplasmas and *Chlamidia trachomatis* [31].

Solasno N.N. Volodina et al. (2010), if until the 90s of the last century, gram-positive microflora, mainly group B streptococcus, prevailed in the etiology of CUP, and then in recent decades the importance of gram-negative bacteria (*Klebsiella*, *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus*, etc.) has increased.) [22].

Alieva A.I. [25] identified several types of clinical course of bacterial pneumonia in newborns, depending on the type of pathogen:

Pneumonia caused by *S. aureus*, *S. epidermidis*

Staphylococcal pneumonia can have many clinical variants. In some cases, it develops as a primary disease with an acute onset, severe and prolonged course. In other cases, the disease is characterized by a gradual, prolonged, undulating course, being a complication of sepsis. In newborns, staphylococcal pneumonia proceeds without abscessing, according to the type of small-focal or interstitial pneumonia. Despite this, such pneumonia in newborns is severe, with severe symptoms of intoxication, high fever, cyanosis, shortness of breath, significant impairment of cardiovascular activity and liver enlargement.

Group B Streptococcus Pneumonia

Streptococcal pneumonia is now rare, possibly due to the fact that hemolytic streptococcus remains highly sensitive to penicillin antibiotics. The disease develops in the early neonatal period, most often in the first 48-72 hours of life. Isolated streptococcal pneumonia is recorded in 30-45% of newborns, it is clinically manifested on the 5th-7th day of a child's life and is often one of the manifestations of congenital (intrauterine) streptococcal sepsis. Pneumonia caused by *S. agalactiae* is characterized by a combination of inflammation in the interstitial lung tissue with the presence of multiple atelectasis, which are detected on chest x-rays, as well as a syndrome of respiratory disorders.

Group B streptococcus (*S. agalactiae*) can be isolated from blood and cerebrospinal fluid [25].

Pneumococcal pneumonia occurs most often at 6 months of age. In children, pneumonia occurs with moderate toxicosis, fever and shortness of breath. X-rays show polysegmental infiltrative changes [25].

Pneumonia caused by *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae* and other gram-negative bacteria of the Enterobacteriaceae family, the main hospital-acquired pneumonia in children. Klebsiella pneumonia is distinguished by the severity of the course, the clinical picture of infectious-toxic shock. The entire left side of the lung is usually affected; characterized by the formation of multiple abscesses. A similar clinical picture is observed in pneumonia caused by various types of enterobacteria, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter*.

In the development of pneumonia caused by *K. pneumoniae* or *E. coli*, importance is attached to microaspiration of mucus infected with pathogens from the upper respiratory tract. Frequent regurgitation in newborns contributes to the colonization of the oropharyngeal mucosa by bacteria [25].

Pneumonia caused by *P. aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter* spp.

Most nosocomial pneumonias are caused by *P. aeruginosa* (poor prognosis, high mortality) and other non-fermenting Gram-negative bacteria. According to Russian scientists, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was detected in infants who died from RNP in 30.1% of cases; *Acinetobacter* spp. (mainly

A. calcoaceticus) - less than 5%. In addition, *P. aeruginosa* is the causative agent of pneumonia in children with cystic fibrosis.

Such diseases are usually extremely complex. Inflammation of the lungs often begins acutely, but sometimes, especially in newborns and premature babies, subacute current is possible. More than 50% of cases develop toxic shock. The lobe of the lung is often affected, possibly microabscess formation [25].

Listeria pneumonia in newborns

The development of the disease in fetuses and newborns with reduced immunity. *Listeria* usually does not cause disease in otherwise healthy people. Fetuses and newborns are infected from mothers as a result of transmission of infection with listeriosis chorioamnionitis or influenza-like listeriosis of a pregnant woman. With antenatal infection, the disease manifests itself in the first 48-72 hours of life, which leads to the development of congenital isolated listeriosis pneumonia or sepsis. With intrapartum infection, isolated meningitis and enterocolitis are common. *Listeria pneumonia* in newborns has no specific clinical and radiological features. The diagnosis is confirmed on the basis of detection of the pathogen or its antigen [25].

Chlamydial pneumonia in newborns

Currently, pneumonia of chlamydial etiology is common (8-10: 1000 newborns). In newborns born with antenatal pneumonia, the Apgar score is below 6 points.

Clinical signs of intrauterine chlamydial pneumonia occur at different times after birth - within 4-12 hours to 4-5 days of life, sometimes up to several months. Symptoms of the disease appear gradually, accompanied by a dry cough, which eventually intensifies and becomes paroxysmal. The general condition does not suffer. Shortness of breath increases gradually. There is a discrepancy between the clinical manifestations of pneumonia (dyspnea, cyanosis), a relatively mild general condition and elementary symptoms of intoxication. However, the vast majority of newborns are diagnosed with hepatosplenomegaly from birth or in the first days of life. In 50% of children, a gray shade of the skin and edematous syndrome of II-III degree are noted.

The clinical picture of lung damage manifests itself over time. Most likely, this is due to a long latent course and activation of the infection under the influence of various factors (hypothermia, overheating, BCG vaccination, artificial feeding, etc.).

In smears from the upper respiratory tract and TBA, chlamydial antigen is detected. Pneumonia is severe, often fatal.

In premature babies, chlamydial infection occurs against the background of severe toxicosis. On the 5-7th day of life, infants develop infectious toxicosis, accompanied by pallor and "marbling" of the skin with severe icterus, sometimes accompanied by a rash. There is depression of the central nervous system, regurgitation. Most newborns have lymphadenopathy.

There is a dissociation between the severity of dyspnea and relatively insufficient physical and radiological data, a dry paroxysmal cough (similar to whooping cough), but without repetition, appears.

Breathing in the lungs is puerile or somewhat weakened, scattered crepitant rales are heard, and rales may appear. On the 2nd-3rd week of the disease, a paroxysmal, wet cough appears with the discharge of viscous sputum. In addition, the persistence of fetal shunts and an increase in cardiopulmonary insufficiency are characteristic. In the most severe cases, hemorrhagic disease of the newborn or DIC syndrome appears. Pneumonia is interstitial in nature, which is explained by the biology of the pathogen and the similarity of its vital functions with viruses [25].

Mycoplasma pneumonia in newborns

The severity of clinical manifestations of mycoplasmal infection is very variable and can be characterized by both subclinical and manifest course. *M. pneumoniae* can affect both the upper and lower respiratory tract. The incubation period for mycoplasma infection is about 2-3 weeks.

In pediatric practice, a gradual onset of the disease is more often observed. In newborns, catarrhal phenomena are noted. The most striking clinical symptom of mycoplasma infection is a dry, paroxysmal, intense cough.

Mycoplasma pneumoniae is different in that extrapulmonary symptoms are often present. These include skin rash, pain in the abdomen, muscles and joints, paresthesia. Rash is detected in 12-15% of sick children. It is maculopapular or urticarial. In young children, the symptoms are mild.

In some patients, the disease has a mixed etiology. In this situation, a secondary bacterial infection joins. Drain pneumonia is most severe when small foci merge with each other, affecting several lung segments or an entire lobe. In half of sick children with pneumonia, an increase in the liver is observed. The function of the organ is not impaired. Rarely, the spleen enlarges [25].

The importance of ureaplasma in the development of NP is discussed in the literature. The fact that the transmission of infection occurs in a vertical way has been confirmed. Culture of *U. urealyticum* is isolated from maternal and umbilical cord blood, from amniotic fluid, ETT of newborns, and from affected lungs of infants [32].

There are differences of opinion regarding the importance of mycoplasmas in the etiology of congenital and neonatal pneumonia. Some researchers deny their role, while others provide opposite evidence [33].

Conclusion. Analyzing the above, it should be concluded that the problem of neonatal pneumonia remains one of the most urgent in modern healthcare due to the severity of the course and high mortality. There is conflicting information regarding the etiological structure, clinical course, and significant risk factors for the implementation of the disease in newborns, which makes it difficult to diagnose early and choose the optimal treatment regimen.

Studies aimed at the isolation and identification of etiopathogens, the study of the biological properties of isolated strains of microorganisms, the analysis of innate immunity factors (TLR2, TLR4, HBD1, HBD-2, TNF α and NF- κ B) at the level of the mucous membranes of the upper respiratory tract during intrauterine infection of the fetus and early neonatal pneumonia, as well as the rationale for the methods of diagnosis and treatment of neonatal pneumonia are topical areas of modern medical science and health care.

Thus, the need to study and solve the above problems ensures the relevance of this topic, the priority of its goals and objectives.

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